

Best Coapproximation in Fuzzy anti-n-Normed Spaces

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Abstract : The main purpose of this paper is to consider the new kind of approximation which is called as t-best coapproximation in fuzzy n-normed spaces. The set of all t-best coapproximation define the t-coproximinal, t-co-Chebyshev and F-best coapproximation and then prove several theorems pertaining to this sets.

Keywords : Fuzzy-n-normed space, t-best coapproximation, t-coproximinal, t-co-Chebyshev, F-best coapproximation, t-orthogonality

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014